

D7.2 - Workshop on industrial and investments priorities for successful AI at the Edge in Europe – Workshop Nr 1

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CFD	Call for Demos
CFP	Call for Papers
PC	Program Committee

Executive Summary

This document describes the preparation, implementation and results of a workshop organized by partners of the dAIEdge Consortium as part of work package 7 “Collaborative Innovation, Benchmarking and Sustainable Development”. This event, which we named ExcelAIEdge25, is the first of four major project-wide events to be organized within this work package.

CONTENTS

1. Introduction	6
2. Preparation	6
3. Implementation	7
3.1. Call for Papers, Call for Demos.....	7
3.2. Workshop website	8
3.3. Paper and demo review process.....	8
3.4. Awards	10
3.5. Final program	11
4. Results.....	13
4.1. Basic Statistics	13
4.2. Pictures of the event.....	15
5. Difficulties	20
6. Next Steps.....	21
ANNEX A: List of related events	22
ANNEX B: Call for Papers and Demos	23

1. Introduction

This document describes the preparation, implementation and results of a workshop organized by partners of the dAIEdge Consortium as part of work package 7 “Collaborative Innovation, Benchmarking and Sustainable Development”. This event, which we named ExcelAIEdge25, is the first of four major project-wide events to be organized within this work package.

Apart from minor difficulties typical of this type of events (reported at the end of the document), the event was considered a success. The full-day workshop packed several sections: invited keynote, paper presentations, demo sessions and an early-matchmaking session.

The document has been organized as follows. Section 2 describes the preparation steps prior to the event. Section 3 describes the execution of the event. Section 4 summarizes results. Finally, for the sake of completeness in Section 5 we report on difficulties encountered.

2. Preparation

The preparation of the event started very early in M7 (8 months prior to the event) with regular meetings by partners involved in WP7. Early on, it was decided to co-locate our event with another major event in Europe, so as to maximize impact. Thus, the first step that was taken was to compile a list of events related to the objectives of dAIEdge, particularly Edge AI or AI in general. This list is in Annex A. For some of the events we inquired about the possibility of co-locating a full-day event, pricing and format options. After internal discussions we decided to select the HiPEAC conference 2025, to be held in Barcelona (Spain), 20-22 January 2025¹. HiPEAC (High Performance and Embedded Architecture and Compilation) is a European network of excellence in computing systems. It aims to advance the field of computing architectures, programming models, design tools, and embedded systems, focusing on innovative and energy-efficient solutions for a wide range of applications, including emerging Edge AI. HiPEAC fosters collaboration among academia, industry, and other stakeholders, helping to bridge the gap between research and commercial applications. HiPEAC is a long-standing network in Europe, having just entered its 20th year of existence. Today, it is one of the largest networks of its kind in Europe, and numbers over 2,000 specialists. For 20 years, HiPEAC has also been shaping EU policy, as described recently by Max Lemke, Head of Unit Internet of Things at the European Commission².

¹ Other events that were seen as particularly relevant during our selection were: World Summit AI, DATE2025 (Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference) and TRANSFIERE 2025 (14th European Meeting on Science, Technology and Innovation).

² “Twenty years of HiPEAC: Shaping European policy on computing innovation since 2004”, Max Lemke. <https://www.hipeac.net/news/7084/twenty-years-of-hipeac-shaping-european-policy-on-computing-innovation-since-2004/>

The annual HiPEAC conference is the flagship event of HiPEAC. Associated workshops, tutorials, special sessions, several large poster sessions and an industrial exhibition run in parallel with the conference. The three-day event attracts over 500+ delegates each year.

On May 3rd, 2024, we submitted a proposal for a dAIEdge workshop to the HiPEAC2025 organization. The proposal was accepted on July 12th, 2024.

3. Implementation

3.1. Call for Papers, Call for Demos

After internal discussions, we decided to make the event more attractive by adopting a format ‘Workshop+Demo+Early matchmaking’. While this required more effort on our side, it was thought that such a format would attract more people. We decided on a short name for our event: **ExcelAIEdge25**.

One of the first steps in the preparation of the event was the writing and dissemination of the customary ‘Call for Papers’ (henceforth CFP) and ‘Call for Demos’ (henceforth CFD). The CFP is an invitation issued by the organization of an event soliciting submissions of technical papers from researchers, practitioners, or experts in a specific field. It serves as a formal announcement of the event and provides the details necessary for potential contributors to prepare and submit their work and, if accepted, attend the event. The CFP of ExcelAIEdge25 is reproduced in Annex B (the Annex shows the first text of the CFP, it does not contain the final invited speakers and deadline extension).

The CFP was disseminated through various means. It was first sent to the full dAIEdge Consortium, and then shared with relevant email lists such as ml-news@googlegroups.com or cvml@lists.auth.gr, through LinkedIn, to relevant organizations such as EurAI, CEA, AEPIA, AERFAI, via Twitter/X³ and through HiPEAC communications channels. The CFP and CFD also featured prominently in ExcelAIEdge25’s dedicated website (see next section).

In line with similar workshops, the CFP solicited papers on work related to Edge Artificial Intelligence. The submission deadline was fixed to November 15th, 2024 (later extended to November 18th, 2024). Besides research papers, the CFP explicitly allowed for case studies, position papers and work-in-progress. As for paper format, the common double-column IEEE format was chosen, with an extension between 4 and 8 pages including references. Papers had to include the authors’ names and affiliations.

In order to maximize participation, the event did not have proceedings. The idea was to encourage the submission of the most recent (possibly still ongoing) work, allowing authors to submit the paper

³ With tags such as @EdgeAI_, @Ai4Csm, @a_iqready, @CleveSocial, @ProjectAeolus, @6gIntense, @EARASHI2022, @AndanteAI, @CharityProj, @AI4SoilHealth, @SmartEdge_EU, @VisionArtif

elsewhere. With the explicit permission of the authors, accepted papers would be posted on the workshop website prior to the event.

For the demo session, we allowed both on-site demos and through a pre-recorded video (with voiceover). In case of a high number of demo proposals, the program committee would make a selection prioritizing on-site demos.

3.2. Workshop website

The main communication channel for any event is arguably its dedicated website. For ExcelAIEdge25 we set up a new domain www.excellence-in-edge-ai.eu. Then the website itself was created with the relevant sections, see Figure 1. The website was already publicly visible by July 2024.

Figure 1. ExcelAIEdge25 website screenshot

3.3. Paper and demo review process

In order to handle the paper review process, an EasyChair license was purchased. EasyChair is a widely used web-based conference management system used for organizing academic and professional events. EasyChair's features include paper submission and tracking and peer review and evaluation workflows and communication (i.e. emailing) tools. Needless to say, the review process is critical, it must adhere to the customary standards of transparency and selection based on merit.

We created a 9-people Program Committee (PC) to carry out the review process:

- Oscar Deniz and Noelia Vallez (UCLM)
- Christos Kozanitis and Giorgos Vasiliadis (FORTH)
- Alessandro Capotondi and Roberto Cavicchioli (UNIMORE)
- Jona Beysens (CSEM)
- Alain Pagani (DFKI)
- Ander Garcia (VICOMTECH)

After the submission period closed, the review process started. A first filter was applied to discard incomplete submissions (such as when paper metadata was submitted but no PDF). A number of papers were also withdrawn by the authors. A total of 24 submissions were retained for review. Some of the submissions came from the consortium partners, whereas others were external. Then, we identified conflicts of interest between the submissions and the PC. After that, submissions were distributed to the PC, ensuring that each paper received two reviews (for a total of 48 reviews). Figure 2 shows the assignment matrix that relates each submission # with the corresponding reviewers. The figure also shows the conflicts of interest that were detected.

	(total)	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	(total)
I prefer not to review it	Vasiliadis					*	*	*	*	*																	5
I want to review this paper	Vallez	*	*	*	*	*																					6
I can review it	Pagani																							*	*	*	5
I have a conflict of interest	Kozanitis					*	*	*	*	*																	6
	Garcia																									*	5
	Deniz	*	*	*	*	*																			*	*	6
	Cavicchioli																										5
	Capotondi																										5
	Beysens																										5
	(submission)	2	3	4	6	7	8	9	12	13	14	15	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	27	29	31	32	(submission)	

Figure 2. Paper review assignment matrix

Each reviewer was asked to provide comments on the paper, including positive and negative aspects, and also provide a numerical score. Figure 3 shows the list of the papers reviewed, along with the final ACCEPT/REJECT decision.

#	Title	Scores	Average	Decision
31	Enhancing Solar Irradiance Forecasts with On-Device Continual Adaptation	2(2),3(4)	2.7	ACCEPT
19	Multiobjective deployment of concurrent gait recognition models in the edge	2(4),3(5)	2.6	ACCEPT
24	Edge Computing vs. GPU-Accelerated Pipelines in Low-Cost Microscopy Applications	2(4),3(5)	2.6	ACCEPT
13	An ultra-low-power CGRA for accelerating Transformers at the edge	1(3),3(4)	2.1	ACCEPT
14	Aurora: the Smart Acoustic Weather Station	1(3),3(4)	2.1	ACCEPT
20	Scalable Virtual Lab for Remote Experiments on AI-powered Edge Devices	3(4),1(3)	2.1	ACCEPT
12	Adaptive Frame-Aware Network for Driver Monitoring Systems	1(3),3(3)	2.0	ACCEPT
17	Towards smart and adaptive agents for active sensing on edge devices	2(4),2(4)	2.0	ACCEPT
23	STEER: Software Toolkit for Edge Efficient Retraining	2(4),2(4)	2.0	ACCEPT
18	A Benchmark Methodology and Evaluation Framework for Edge Accelerators	3(4),1(5)	1.9	ACCEPT
27	3CSD MLOps: Enhancing Edge MLOps with Computational Storage for Efficient Model Maintenance and Intelligent Triage Systems	0(4),3(5)	1.7	ACCEPT
9	Autonomous Coffee Delivery Robot Using PRM and A* Path Planning	1(3),2(2)	1.4	ACCEPT
15	FPGA Accelerator for Training Bio-inspired Architecture in Deep Neural Networks with Dendritic Structures	2(4),1(5)	1.4	ACCEPT
29	GuardONNX: Machine Learning Inference within Trusted Execution Environments	1(5),2(2)	1.3	ACCEPT
25	Dynamic Reconfiguration of Deep Neural Networks for Resource-Constrained FPGA Edge Accelerators	2(4),0(4)	1.0	ACCEPT
21	eXtended Reality for Enhanced Remote Human-Robot Interaction: A Virtual Interface based on Gesture Recognition	-1(3),2(5)	0.9	REJECT
2	Evaluating Point Cloud Feature Extraction: Traditional vs. Deep Learning Techniques	0(5),1(4)	0.4	REJECT
32	Automated Neural Network Learning Distribution Across Multiple Machines	1(3),-3(5)	-1.5	REJECT
3	Advancing Telemedicine Through Artificial Intelligence: Transformative Trends in Diagnostic Accuracy and Personalized Care	-3(5),-2(4)	-2.6	REJECT
4	Error-Bound Analysis and Simulation of the BB84 Quantum Key Exchange Protocol on IBM's Q Simulator	-3(5),-2(4)	-2.6	REJECT
8	Jovial: Astronomical Data Analysis Cloud Service	-2(3),-3(5)	-2.6	REJECT
6	Advanced Neural Video Captioning	-3(5),-3(4)	-3.0	REJECT
7	Understanding Multi-Tenancy in SaaS	-3(5),-3(4)	-3.0	REJECT
22	EDGE AI: TOOLS AND METHODOLOGIES FOR DISTRIBUTED INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS	-3(4),-3(5)	-3.0	REJECT

Figure 3. List of reviewed papers

For the demos, an online form was created to request demo proposals. This form had the following fields:

- Name of the person proposing the demo
- Institution
- Email address
- Describe your demo
- Give a title to your demo
- Are you sending a paper to the workshop? (either related or unrelated to the demo)
- Will the proposed demo be in situ or online?
- What materials or infrastructures are needed for the demo?
- What materials or infrastructure (of those needed) will you be providing?

A total of 9 demo proposals were received, all from consortium partners. The demos appear later in this document (section on Final program).

3.4. Awards

In order to attract submissions and demo proposals, the CFP and CFD made a provision for a best paper award and also a best demo award (diploma and 300€ each). However, it was clearly indicated that money would be only given if the winner was unrelated to the dAIEDGE Consortium.

3.5. Final program

Figure 4 shows the final program for ExcelAIEdge25.

- 10:00 – 11:00 Keynote: “LLMs at the Edge: Challenges and Promises for Real-Time Intelligence”, Alireza Dehghani
- 11:00 - 11:30 [Coffee break]
- 11:30 – 13:00 Paper presentations ([papers #19, 24, 13, 14, 20, 12, 17, 23](#))
- 13:00 - 14:00 [Buffet lunch]
- 14:00 – 15:05 Paper presentations ([papers #18, 27, 9, 15, 29, 25, 31](#))
- 15:05 – 15:30 Demos, 1/2
- Stan, the personal home assistant
 - dAIEdge-VLab: Scalable Virtual Lab for Remote Experiments on AI-powered Edge Devices
 - STEER: Software Toolkit for Edge Efficient Retraining
- 15:30 - 16:00 [Coffee break]
- 16:00 – 16:50 Demos, 2/2
- The Aurora Acoustic Weather Station
 - Towards smart and adaptive agents for active sensing on edge devices
 - The OpenFlexure Microscope
 - Rupia: A Remote Access Hardware-In-The-Loop Tool for the Myriad X VPU
 - eXtended Reality for Enhanced Remote Human-Robot Interaction: A Virtual Interface based on Gesture Recognition
 - Weapon detector from thermal images
- 16:50 – 17:20 Matchmaking Session:
- “Industrial investment priorities for successful AI at the Edge in Europe”, Jean-Marc Bonnefous, 20 min
 - “Transforming Satellite Services through On-Board Edge Compute”, Maria Buckley (Ubotica Technologies), 10 min
- 17:20 - 17:30 Best Paper Award

Figure 4. Final program of ExcelAIEdge25

The invited speaker was Dr. Alireza Dehghani, see Figure 5.

Dr **Alireza Dehghani** is an AI Technical Programme Manager (TPGM) at CeADAR, Ireland's Centre for AI, where he leads multiple cutting-edge projects in AI, machine learning, and edge computing. With over two decades of experience in industry and academia, Alireza has spearheaded initiatives in AI-driven solutions, including research on the applications of Large Language Models (LLMs), real-time intelligence at the edge, AI Digital Twins, and Sustainable AI. He has worked extensively on bridging the gap between AI research and industry, contributing to digital transformation, healthcare, and smart systems innovation. Alireza is also the Principal Investigator on several national and European-funded projects, collaborating with international partners to advance AI's role in industry. He is passionate about exploring the intersection of AI and real-world challenges, making significant contributions to research and practical applications.

Figure 5. Invited speaker

Keynote #1: LLMs at the Edge, Dr. Alireza Dehghani, University College Dublin

Dr Dehghani's keynote presentation was about the industrial potential of LLMs at the edge.

The presentation illustrated the transformational impact of bringing LLM technology into edge devices and showcased a number of emerging applications both for the industry and the consumer markets: mobile agents, wearable devices, coding & debugging, hardware, software applications,

optimizers, etc. The confluence of LLMs and end user applications provides fertile ground for successful products developed by European start-ups and enterprises.

For the early-matchmaking session we heard two Keynote presentations, one setting up the context and the challenges to growing industrial applications for Edge AI, the other one from the perspective a successful SME active in the critical Space sector.

Keynote #2: Closing the Resources Gaps for Edge AI in Europe, Jean-Marc Bonnefous (BCA)

J. M. Bonnefous, dAIEdge's Exploitation Manager, presented the significant growth to be expected in the European Edge AI Market. Mr Bonnefous bases Europe's needs to fill the gaps in this field on 4 pillars: skills, infrastructure, capital and regulation. Specialist resources are hard to find and costs are increasing in a compute 'arms race. With respect to the last two pillars, he emphasized that access to capital is still Europe's main pain point in relation to other regions and flagged the need to increase access to funding markets for projects and start-ups. He also raised some concerns with respect to the regulatory environment and warned of increased risks of regulatory arbitrage between different regions and countries, in what he called the rise of 'AI nationalism'. On a positive note, he also presented a number of initiatives aiming at closing these gaps, in particular versus the US and Chinese initiatives. It was proposed that the European 'edge' in global markets relies on its academic excellence in some selected domains, and the more decentralized and ethics-orientated approach that Europe is taking, facing the more centralized US and Chinese business models. Edge AI could indeed be one of Europe's edge.

Keynote #3: SME presentation, M. Buckley (UBOTICA)

M. Buckley (Ubotica Technologies Ltd.) described Ubotica's activity and prospects in the emerging domain of 'AI in space'. Space is obviously the ultimate 'edge' where AI can be deployed.

ExcelAIEdge25 Best Paper Award

The best paper award was given, at the end of the event, to the paper that received the highest average scores during the review (and was presented at the event), see Figure 6.

Funded by
the European Union

On behalf of the Organizing Committee

Oscar Deniz
Full Professor

Figure 6. Best paper award

4. Results

4.1. Basic Statistics

- The project website received a total of 833 visits, with most visits coming from outside Europe.
- Upon closing of the deadline, the workshop received a total of 30 submissions. From 24 papers reviewed, 15 were accepted for presentation at the event (62.5% acceptance ratio, 50% of the submissions). Figure 7 shows statistics by country.

country	authors	submitted	accepted	acceptance rate	PC members
Belgium	4	0.83	0.83	1.00	-
France	1	1.00	1.00	1.00	-
Germany	4	0.83	0.83	1.00	1
Greece	11	3.00	3.00	1.00	2
India	4	2.00	0.00	0.00	-
Ireland	6	1.69	1.69	1.00	-
Italy	3	1.33	1.33	1.00	2
Nigeria	3	1.00	0.00	0.00	-
Pakistan	2	1.00	0.00	0.00	-
Poland	2	0.67	0.67	1.00	-
Spain	20	4.18	2.18	0.52	3
Switzerland	9	1.96	1.96	1.00	1
Tunisia	2	0.40	0.40	1.00	-
United Kingdom	1	0.11	0.11	1.00	-
United States	1	4.00	1.00	0.25	-

Figure 7. Submission statistics by country. Note that some numbers appear as non-integer values because of co-authorship across countries.

- According to HiPEAC 2025 organization records, 178 people (from 103 institutions in 32 countries) registered to attend ExcelAIEdge25.
- The following organisations were registered for the dAIEdge workshop (actual attendance to the workshop was not measured):

Linköping University, BSC, International University of Rabat (UIR), DFKI, Semmelweis University, Collins Aerospace, PoliTo, UPM, U.Porto, University College Dublin, University of Manchester, University of Sarajevo, Inside IA, ARM, AACISA, Jülich Research Centre, ISI, NTUA, Axelera AI, IIT Delhi, HUST, AMD, University of Edinburgh, DENSO, Imperial College London, Beijing Institute of Technology, NUDT, fortiss, TU Berlin, INRIA, Keimyung, TU Dresden, NTUA, ICCS, CiTIUS, Qualcomm, Mälardalen University (MDH), UPV, IBM Research Haifa, Openchip, Vicomtech, RWTH Aachen, University of Groningen, Huawei Research Germany, LINKS Foundation, Almeida Rodriguez, ULL, Complutense University of Madrid, HIRO, IMDEA, University of Cagliari, IMDEA, University of Pisa, Snap Inc., UCC Ireland, UCY, EXAPSYS, University of Zagreb, BCA, Bielefeld University, Ubotica, Huawei Sweden, RPTU Kaiserslautern, University of Malaga, University of Glasgow, University of Barcelona, University of Twente, UBO, UNIMORE, FORTH, Khalifa University, Jiao Tong University, DataPower, UCLM, BUT, CEA, Unical, Politehnica University of Timisoara, CNR, Poznań University of Technology, uni.lu, Lakeside Labs, INFN, UPC, University of Lübeck, UBS, University of Auckland, ULL, NXP, University of Utah, Tokyo Tech, UNIMI, Collins Aerospace, Tinedo, UNISI, UPM, TU Munich, SaKTH, University of Murcia, University of Thessaly, IMDEA, ARCTUR, IMEC, Aalto University, University of L'Aquila, HUST, NUDT

4.2. Pictures of the event

Figure 8. Keynote presentation

Figure 9. Another Keynote presentation

Decentralized 'AI-On-Demand': An Alternative Model

Limitations of the Cloud Model
 Latency issues
 Limited model portability
 Privacy concerns
 Bandwidth costs

Feature	Centralized System	Decentralized System
Single Point of Failure	Yes	No
Transparency	Limited	Increased
User Control	Limited	Enhanced
Censorship Risk	High	Reduced

Enabling Collaboration
 Democratize access to resources
 Allow for accelerated innovation and competition
 Collaboration between industry and academia
 Create incentive mechanisms
 Digital Marketplaces can provide a more open heterogeneous delivery

Figure 10. View of the workshop room

Figure 11. One of the paper presentations

Figure 92. One of the live demos (Concealed weapon detector from thermal images)

Figure 10. Best paper award

Figure 11. dAIEdge participants at the event

5. Difficulties

For the sake of completeness, this section reports on the difficulties encountered during the preparation or execution of the event. Perhaps the major setback was the late cancellation of three speakers that had been invited:

- Christoph Posch (Prophesee)
- Emmanuel Aldeguer (Axone)
- Alessandro De Carli (Acurast)

The first one had been considered for a keynote, while the other two were going to participate in the early matchmaking session. The reasons given for the cancellations were various. In one of the cases the invited speaker had to attend a project review meeting organized by the EC that was set for the same day as our event. The other one was invited to talk at the World Economic Forum in Davos the same day.

On the other hand, one of the accepted papers was not presented at the event:

Autonomous Coffee Delivery Robot Using PRM and A Path Planning*, by Sufiyan Ahmed Mohammed

The corresponding author did not respond to emails from the Program Chair.

Finally, we report on the minor issue encountered by partners presenting one of the demos. Their demo was to show a smartphone-based app that, using a miniature thermal camera, can detect concealed handguns. Unfortunately, due to legal regulations in Spain they could not bring their realistic (but not real) handgun to the event. However, the demonstration went well with a Lego handgun.

6. Next Steps

The ExcelAIEdge25 workshop is the first project-wide event organized by the dAIEdge project within the Work Package 7 “Collaborative Innovation, Benchmarking and Sustainable Development”. Another three events will be organized within this work package to further this effort. The ExcelAIEdge25 event was focused on the academic and research phase of the industrial value chain towards the successful development of Edge AI in Europe and provided a basic framework and identified some challenges and gaps; the next events will be more focused on concrete matchmaking and demo opportunities between academia, projects, SMEs and investors.

ANNEX A: List of related events

This is a list of events related to dAIEdge’s objectives. This list was used to select the event in which to co-locate our workshop.

ID	Event	Web	Date1	Date	Venue	Interval
1	International Federation for Information Processing (IFIP) Networking Conference	https://networking.ifip.org/2024/	03-06 June 2024	2024/06	Thessaloniki, Greece	Yearly
2	8th IEEE International Conference on Fog and Edge Computing	https://icfec2024.ontariotechu.ca/	06-09 May, 2024	2024/05	Philadelphia, USA	Yearly
3	World Summit AI	https://worldsummit.ai/	09 – 10 October 2024	2024/10	Amsterdam, Netherlands	Yearly
4	International Conference on Embedded Wireless Systems and Networks	https://ewsn24.tii.ae/	10th-13th December 2024	2024/12	Abu Dhabi, UAE	Yearly
5	ETSI IoT Conference	https://www.etsi.org/events/2088-etsi-iot-conf-2022	11-13 October 2022	2022/10	Sophia Antipolis, France	1-2 years
6	Data Week	https://data-week.eu/2023-edition	13 – 15 June 2023	2023/06	Luleå, Sweden	?
7	IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing	https://2024.ieeeicassp.org/	14~19 April 2024	2024/04	Seoul, Korea	Yearly
8	HIPEAC conference	http://hipeac.net/2025/barcelona	January 2025	2025/1	Barcelona, Spain	Yearly
9	Wireless World Research Forum	eeai	17-18 April 2024	2024/04	Berlin, Germany	Yearly
10	European Conference on EDGE AI Technologies and Applications – EEAI	https://edge-ai-tech.eu/program-2024/	21-23 October 2024	2024/10	Cagliari, Sardinia, Italy	Yearly
11	AI Hardware & Edge AI Summit Europe	https://aihwedgesummit-europe.com/events/ai-hardware-edge-ai-summit-europe	18 - 19 June 2024	2024/06	London, UK	Yearly
12	LEADING AND MANAGING IN THE DIGITAL ERA:: Shaping the Future of Work and Business Education	https://lmdc2023.org/	19 - 20 June 2023	2023/06	Athens, Greece	?
13	Embedded Vision Summit	https://embeddedvisionsummit.com	21 - 23 May 2024	2024/05	Santa Clara, California, USA	Yearly
14	ITF World	https://www.imecif.com/2023/world	21-22 May 2023	2023/05	Antwerp, Belgium	Yearly
15	European Forum for Electronic Components and Systems	https://efecs.eu/	24 - 25 November 2022	2022/11	Amsterdam, Netherlands	?
16	9th IEEE International Conference on Network Softwareization	https://netsoft2023.ieee-netsoft.org/	24–28 June 2024	2024/06	St. Louis, USA	Yearly
17	4th International Conference on Internet of Things	https://www.iciot.in/	26 - 28 April 2023	2023/04	Chennai, India	1-2 years
18	IEEE International Conference on Cloud Networking	https://cloudnet2024.ieee-cloudnet.org/	27–29 November 2024	2024/11	Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	Yearly
19	European Conference on Networks and Communications	https://www.eucnc.eu/	3 - 6 June 2024	2024/06	Antwerp, Belgium	Yearly
20	Mobile World Conference	https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/	3-6 March 2025	2025/03	Barcelona, Spain	Yearly
21	IEEE International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks	https://camad2024.ieee-camad.org/	6–8 November 2023	2023/11	Athens, Greece	Yearly
22	IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking	https://cscn2023.ieee-cscn.org/	6–8 November 2023	2023/11	Munich, Germany	Yearly
23	22nd IEEE International Symposium on Parallel and Distributed Computing	https://www.fhcr.ch/ispdc2024	8-10 July 2023	2023/07	Chur, Switzerland	Yearly
24	embedded world Conference	https://www.embedded-world.de/en	11-13 March 2025	2025/03	Nuremberg, Germany	Yearly
25	Edge World Summit	https://www.edgecomputingworld.com	April 2 & 3, 2024	2024/04	Silicon Valley	Yearly
26	EuroSys	https://2024.eurosys.org/	April 22nd-25th 2024	2024/04	Athens, Greece	Yearly
27	7th Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing Conference	https://www.aiccc.net/	December 14-16, 2024	2024/12	Tokyo, Japan	Yearly
28	IEEE IEDGE 2023 SYMPOSIUM ON INTELLIGENT EDGE COMPUTING AND COMMUNICATIONS	https://services.conferences.computer.org/2024/	July 7-13, 2024	2024/07	Sherzhen, China	Yearly
29	IEEE International Symposium on Information Theory (ISIT)	https://2024.ieee-isit.org/home	July 7 - 12 2024	2024/07	Athens, Greece	Yearly
30	International Conference on Hybrid Human-Artificial Intelligence	https://hhai-conference.org/2024/	June 10-14 2024	2024/06	Malmö, Sweden	Yearly
31	27th Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks	https://www.icin-conference.org/	March 11-14, 2024	2024/03	Paris, France	Yearly
32	4th IEEE International Conference on Autonomic Computing and Self-Organizing Systems	https://2024.acsos.org/	Mon 16 - Fri 20 September 2024	2024/09	Aarhus, Denmark	Yearly
33	31st IEEE International Conference on Network Protocols	https://icnp24.cs.ucr.edu/	October 28-31, 2024	2024/10	Charleroi, Belgium	Yearly
34	15TH INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON ULTRA MODERN TELECOMMUNICATIONS AND CONTROL SYSTEMS	https://icumt.info/2023/	October 30 - November 1, 2023	2023/11	Ghent, Belgium	?
35	IoT Week	https://iowweek.org/	Posponed to 2024	2024/xx	?	?
36	Transfere, Foro Europeo para la Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación	https://transfere.fycma.com/	20-22 March 2024	2024/03	Malaga, Spain	?
37	Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference (DATE)	https://www.date-conference.com/date-2025-call-papers	31 March - 2 April 2025	2025/03	Lyon, France	Yearly
38	ACM International Conference on the Foundations of Software Engineering (FSE) (WS: The 4th International Workshop on Software Engineering and AI for Data Quality in Cyber-Physical Systems/Internet of Things)	https://2024.esec-fse.org/	15 - 19 July 2024	2024/07	Porto de Galinhas, Brazil	Yearly
39	ICML - International Conference on Machine Learning	https://icml.cc/Conferences/FutureMeetings	2025	2025	Vancouver, Canada	Yearly
40	Information Architecture Conference (IAC)	https://www.theiaconference.com/	9-13 April 2024	2024/04	Seattle, WA, USA	
41	MPLS SD & AI Net World congress	https://www.uppersideconferences.com/mpls-sdn-nfv/	9/10/11 APRIL 2024	2024/04	Paris, France	
42	International Conference on Computing, Machine Learning and Data Science (CMLDS 2024)	http://www.cmlds.net/	12-14 April 2024	2024/04	Singapore	
43	18th European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV 2024)	https://eccv.ecva.net/	Sun Sep 29th through Fri Oct 4th, 2024	2024/10	Milano, Italy	Biyearly
44	27th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR 2024)	https://icpr2024.org/	01-05 Dec 2024	2024/12	Kolkata, India	Yearly
45	IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)	https://www.aconf.org/conf_178954.html	Oct. 26 - Nov 01, 2025	2025/11	Xian, China	Biyearly
46	AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence	https://aaai.org/aaai-conference/	22-25 Feb 2024	2024/02	VANCOUVER, CANADA	Yearly
47	IEEE International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR)	https://icprs.org/	18-18 July 2024	2024/07	London, UK	Yearly
48	IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)	https://2024.ieeeicip.org/	27-30 Oct 2024	2024/10	Abu Dhabi, UAE	Yearly
49	ICLR 2025 - The Twelfth International Conference on Learning Representations	https://waset.org/learning-representations-conference-in-august-2025-in-sydney	August 30-31, 2025	2025/08	Sydney, Australia	Yearly
50	The ACM Conference Series on Recommender Systems (RecSys)	https://recsys.acm.org/recsys24/	14–18 October 2024	2024/10	Bari, Italy	Yearly
51	European Conference on Machine Learning and Principles and Practice of Knowledge Discovery in Databases (ECML PKDD)	https://ecmlpkdd.org/2024/	SEPTEMBER 9 TO 13 2024	2024/09	Vilnius, Lithuania	Yearly
52	European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ECAI)	https://ecai2025.org/	October 27-31, 2025	2025/10	Bologna, Italy	Yearly
53	European Conference on Information Retrieval (ECIR)	https://www.ecir2024.org/	24th-28th March, 2024	2024/03	Glasgow, Scotland	Yearly
54	AMLD EPFL (Applied Machine Learning Days)	https://2024.appliedmldays.org/	March 23-26, 2024	2024/03	Lausanne, Switzerland	?
55	Big Data & AI World Barcelona	https://eshow.es/barcelona/bdaiv	13 - 14 MAYO 2024	2024/05	Barcelona, Spain	Yearly
56	Big Data & AI World Madrid	https://www.bigdataworld.es/	16 y 17 de octubre de 2024	2024/10	Madrid, Spain	Yearly
57	ICPRAM - 14th International Conference on Pattern Recognition Applications and Methods	https://icpram.scitevents.org/	23-25 February 2025	2025/02	Porto, Portugal	
58	International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence	https://ijcai24.org/	Aug 3 - Aug 9, 2024	2024/02	Jeju, Korea	Yearly

ANNEX B: Call for Papers and Demos

Excellence in Artificial Intelligence and Edge Computing

Co-located with the [HiPEAC 2025 Conference](#)

20 January 2025

Barcelona, Spain

The convergence of AI and edge computing represents a new era of technological advances, where the immediacy of data processing and the sophistication of AI algorithms lead to new products and services. Industries are rapidly adopting edge AI applications to streamline costs, automate complex processes, enhance decision-making capabilities, and refine operational efficiency. These applications are not just theoretical constructs; they are real-world solutions that are reshaping industries.

This workshop is dedicated to exploring the frontiers of the AI and edge computing synergy, focusing on the development of scalable and robust AI systems. The workshop is organized and supported by the dAIEdge European Network of Excellence on “AI at the Edge”. In order to make the workshop more interactive and lively, there will be a matchmaking session and a demo session. In the latter, participants will be able to show live demos, either on-site or with a video, of their research and results. Participants in any session will be automatically invited to participate in and benefit from dAIEdge’s network of excellence.

Topics of interest include (but are not limited to):

- Edge AI-based applications, use cases, products and services
- Edge AI tools and methodologies
- Computer vision: image classification, object detection, semantic segmentation, etc.
- Edge AI natural language processing, speech recognition and synthesis
- Energy optimization for edge AI devices
- Reconfigurable edge AI
- Optimization and approximation methods and techniques for edge neural networks
- Multimodal learning for edge AI
- Federated learning
- Edge AI accelerators and HW (GPUs, NPUs, TPUs, ASICs, FPGAs, RISC-V, etc.)
- Edge AI hardware-software co-design methods and tools
- Neuromorphic HW Architectures
- Smart connectivity at the edge
- Edge AI for immersive technologies (XR/VR/AR/MR, metaverse/omniverse/multiverse)
- Simulation and analysis techniques for edge AI
- Generative edge AI
- Transformers at the edge: data, hardware, and software engineering challenges

- Trustworthy edge AI (security, privacy, reliability, explainability, interpretability, etc.)
- Edge AI verification, validation and testing
- Benchmarking edge AI models
- Ethical implications of edge AI

Important dates:

Submission deadline: 15 November 2024

Notification to authors: 6 December 2024

Early bird registration (provisional): 25 December 2024

Submissions:

Papers will be reviewed by the workshop's technical program committee according to criteria regarding a submission's quality, relevance to the workshop's topics, and, foremost, its potential to spark discussions about directions, insights, and solutions on the topics mentioned above. Research papers, case studies, position papers and work-in-progress are all welcome. Authors will retain all rights to submit the work elsewhere. Submitted papers will be given the opportunity to participate in the demo session at the end of the day.

Papers should be in double column [IEEE format](#) of between 4 and 8 pages including references. Papers should be uploaded as PDF and not anonymized. At least one of the authors must register at the conference and attend the workshop to present the paper if it is accepted. There will be a best paper award with diploma and 300€ (the latter will only be awarded if the authors of the best paper are not part of the dAIEdge Consortium). The selection of the best paper will be made by the PC, it will consider the presentation made at the workshop and it will be irrevocable.

[Submission site](#)

For demos only (without paper submission), see Section 'Call for Demos'.

Call for Demos:

The demo session will take place at the end of the day. The demos will be either on-site or through a pre-recorded video (with voiceover). Demo proposers do not need to submit a paper to the workshop. The demo should be, in any case, related to the topics of the workshop, and should not last more than 20 minutes.

If the number of demos submitted is too high the program committee will make a selection, prioritizing on-site demos.

There will be a best demo award with diploma and 300€ (the latter will only be awarded if the authors of the best demo are not part of the dAIEdge Consortium). The selection of the best demo will be made by the PC, it will consider the presentation made at the workshop and it will be irrevocable.

To propose a demo, please [fill out this form](#).

Invited Speakers:

[to be announced]

Program:

[to be announced]

Organizers:

- Deutsches Forschungszentrum Fur Kunstliche Intelligenz Gmbh (DFKI), Germany
- Blekinge Tekniska Hogskola (BTH), Sweden
- Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA), France
- Centre d'Excellence en Technologies de l'Information et de la Communication (CETIC), Belgium
- Deutsche Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e. V. (DLR), Germany
- Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e. V., Germany
- FundingBox Accelerator Sp. z o.o., Poland
- Idryma Technologias Kai Erevnas (FORTH), Greece
- Hipert Srl, Italy
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- Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et en Automatique (INRIA), France
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- Thales SIX GTS France SAS, France
- Ubotica Technologies Limited, Ireland
- University of Castilla-La Mancha (UCLM), Spain
- Università degli Studi di Modena e Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), Italy
- University of Salamanca (USAL), Spain
- Varjo Technologies Oy, Finland
- VERSES Global BV, Netherlands

- Centro de Tecnologías de Interacción Visual y Comunicaciones, Vicomtech, Spain
- Aegis Rider AG, Switzerland
- Bonseyes Community Association, Switzerland
- Centre suisse d'électronique et de microtechnique (CSEM), Switzerland
- Eidgenoessische Technische Hochschule Zuerich (ETHZ), Switzerland
- Haute école spécialisée de Suisse occidentale (HE-SO), Switzerland
- The University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom
- University of Glasgow, United Kingdom

Programme Committee:

Oscar Deniz and Noelia Vallez (UCLM)

Christos Kozanitis and Giorgos Vasiliadis (FORTH)

Alessandro Capotondi and Roberto Cavicchioli (UNIMORE)

Jona Beysens (CSEM)

Alain Pagani (DFKI)

Ander Garcia (VICOMTECH)

Contact

If you have any questions, please feel free to send an email to the workshop chair:
oscar.deniz@uclm.es.

daiedge.eu